

A significant difference in the reaction mechanism of the first step of the aminoacylation reaction in class I and class II synthetases

Sindrila Dutta Banik, Sudarshan Debnath and Nilashis Nandi*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

E-mail : nilashisnandi@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-25828282

Manuscript received 10 January 2012, accepted 22 February 2012

Abstract : Aminoacylation reaction is a vital step of protein synthesis. The reaction takes place within the active site of aminoacyl tRNA synthetase (aaRS) and involves amino acid (AA) as well as adenosine triphosphate (ATP) as substrate. The twenty aaRSs are divided into two classes based on their primary structural sequence as well as three dimensional structures. Several differences in the structures and the reaction mechanism of the second step of aminoacylation reaction of two classes of aaRS are well known. However, no significant difference is reported in the mechanism of first step of aminoacylation reaction of class I and class II aaRSs to the best of our knowledge. The aim of the present work is to analyze the microscopic details of the structure of the reactant state and product (adenylate) state of the first step of aminoacylation reaction for class I and class II aaRSs and relate with the reaction mechanism of the activation step. The present study revealed a significant difference between class I (GluRS, GlnRS, TyrRS, TrpRS, LeuRS, ValRS, IleRS, CysRS, MetRS) and class II aaRSs (HisRS, LysRS, ProRS, AspRS, AsnRS, AlaRS, GlyRS, PheRS, ThrRS) based on the crystal structure analysis and quantum mechanical analysis of electrostatic potential. We show for the first time that the modes of nucleophilic attack in the activation step in class I and class II aaRSs are significantly different. The *syn* oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group of AA attacks in case of class I aaRSs while the *anti* oxygen atom perform the same job for class II aaRSs. The approach of *syn* oxygen atom is favorable for class I aaRS while for class II aaRSs the approach of *anti* oxygen is more favorable in reactant state. Quantum mechanical calculation of electrostatic potential explains the hitherto unknown microscopic differences in the reaction mechanism in the two cases.

Keywords : Aminoacylation, active site, aminoacyl tRNA, synthetase.

Introduction

Protein biosynthesis takes place in successive stages such as aminoacylation followed by initiation, elongation, termination, release, folding and posttranslational processing^{1,2}. The relationship between an amino acid (AA) and its cognate tRNA is established in the aminoacylation reaction. This reaction is vital and links the realm of the protein and the RNA world. The reaction occurs in two steps^{3,4}. The first step is the amino acid activation with the formation of aminoacyl adenylate and release of inorganic pyrophosphate. The second step is charging of the tRNA in which the aminoacyl group is transferred to the tRNA bearing the triplet anticodons of the genetic code. Both activation and charging of twenty natural amino acids are catalyzed by twenty aminoacyl tRNA synthetase (aaRS).

The aaRSs are categorized into two classes (class I and class II). They are different in several respects start-

ing from their primary sequences to the higher level structural organization³⁻⁷. For example, the class I aaRSs are monomeric in general while the class II aaRS are dimers or tetramers. In addition to this structural difference of the active site of aaRS, the mode of binding of acceptor arm of tRNA also differs for the two classes. The class I aaRS interacts with the acceptor stem of tRNA via the minor groove side whereas class II aaRSs use the major groove side to interact with the tRNA. The 3'-terminal tetranucleotide (73-76) form a hairpin structure in class I aaRS and extended conformation in the class II aaRS. The classes further can be subdivided into subclasses based on structural resemblance of catalytic and non-catalytic domain and their compositions. The active site of class I aaRSs contain Rossmann-fold catalytic domain, is composed by parallel β -sheet surrounded by α -helix whereas the active sites of class II aaRSs are built by anti-parallel β -sheets surrounded by β -helices. Interestingly despite

the diversity of the active site structure, the general schemes of the two steps reaction are invariant in all 20 aaRS as shown in Fig. 1. A significant microscopic difference in the reaction mechanism of the second step of aminoacylation reaction for the class I and class II aaRSs

atom (α P) of the ATP for both class I and class II aaRSs. This is also confirmed by the electronic structure based analysis for HisRS^{8,9}. However, no comparative study of the reactant state of AA and ATP during the first step of aminoacylation reaction in the active sites of two differ-

Step 1 : Amino acid activation : Amino acid (AA) + Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) + aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase (aaRS) = aminoacyl-adenylate (AA-AMP) + inorganic pyrophosphate (PPi)

Step 2 : tRNA charging : AA-AMP + aaRS + RNA = aminoacyl-tRNA (AA-tRNA) + Adenosine monophosphate (AMP) + aaRS

Fig. 1. The reaction scheme of the first step (activation step) and second step (tRNA charging) of aminoacylation reaction.

is already noted. The class I enzymes attach the corresponding amino acid to the 2'-OH group of 3'-terminal adenosine of tRNA, whereas class II enzymes (except PheRS) attach the amino acid to the 3'-OH group of the same⁷. However, there is no reported difference in the reaction mechanism of class I and class II aaRSs, to the best of our knowledge. Crystallographic studies proposed that the activation step follows an in-line displacement mechanism in which the oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group of the amino acid attacks to the α -phosphate

ent classes of aaRS is carried out so far. The aim of the present study is to find any microscopic difference in the reaction mechanism of the first step of aminoacylation reaction for the class I and class II aaRSs as already known for the second step.

We analyzed the geometry of the oxygen atoms of the substrate AA, as it approach towards the α P of ATP, based on the crystal structure of the reactant state. The product (adenylate) state is also analyzed for first step of aminoacylation reaction of various class I and class II

aaRSs. Two oxygen atoms of the carboxylic acid group of the substrate AA can adopt four possible conformations with respect to the amino group. The conformations are *syn-periplaner* (*sp*), *syn-clinal* (*sc*), *anti-clinal* (*ac*) and *anti-periplaner* (*ap*)¹⁰. The analysis indicates a significant difference in the reaction mechanism of the first step of aminoacylation reaction for class I (GluRS, GlnRS, TyrRS, TrpRS, LeuRS, ValRS, IleRS, CysRS, MetRS) and class II aaRSs (HisRS, LysRS, ProRS, AspRS, AsnRS, AlaRS, GlyRS, PheRS, ThrRS). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of the difference. We also analyze the origin of the difference in the reaction of activation step based on electrostatic potential. In the next section, we present the computational methods.

Computational methods

The available crystal structure of various class I and class II aaRSs of the reactant state as well as product state of activation step of aminoacylation reaction (such as reactant state of GluRS (2CV1.PDB), GlnRS (1QRU.PDB; 1ZJW.PDB), TyrRS (1H3E.PDB) and TrpRS (1MAU.PDB) belongs to class I HisRS (1KMN.PDB), LysRS (1E24.PDB), ProRS (1H4Q.PDB) belongs to class II as well as adenylate state of GluRS (1N78.PDB), GlnRS (1QTQ.PDB), LeuRS (1OBC.PDB), ValRS (1GAX.PDB), IleRS (1JZQ.PDB), TyrRS (3TS1.PDB), CysRS (3C8Z.PDB), MetRS (2CT8.PDB) belongs to class I and HisRS (1KMM.PDB), AspRS (1COA.PDB), AsnRS (2XGT.PDB), AlaRS (3HXY.PDB), GlyRS (1GGM.PDB), PheRS (1B7Y.PDB), ThrRS (1KOG.PDB) belongs to class II) are used for the present study¹¹⁻³⁰. The crystal structure of the reactant state of LysRS contains both substrate amino acid and ATP. The crystal structures of GluRS, TyrRS, HisRS and ProRS contains the corresponding alcohol (glutaminol, tyrosinol, histidinol and prolinol, respectively) instead of the respective substrate amino acids. The hydroxyl methyl group (-CH₂OH) of the glutaminol, tyrosinol, histidinol and prolinol, respectively, are replaced by the carboxylate anion (-COO⁻ group) for GluRS, TyrRS, HisRS and ProRS. The crystal structure of TrpRS is complexed with ATP and tryptophanamide. The amide group (-CONH₂) of tryptophanamide is replaced by the -COO⁻ group for TrpRS. As the negative charge is delocalized over the two oxygen atoms of the carboxylic acid group, it is expected that the separation between the carbon atom and two oxygen atoms would be same. Consequently the C=O

bond lengths of the carboxylate group of substrate amino acid is set as 1.25 Å (average separation) for all aaRSs. The two crystal structures of the reactant state of GlnRS are individually complexed with ATP, and AMP, amino acid. The position of the ATP is mapped from the 1QRU.PDB to 1ZJW.PDB.

During the activation step of aminoacylation reaction one oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group of substrate AA attacks α P atom of ATP. Since there exist a pair of oxygen atoms of the carboxylic group, each is a possible candidate to attack the α P atom of ATP. The pair of oxygen atoms of the carboxylic group of substrate AA in reactant state can have two possible conformations with respect to the α -amino group of substrate amino acid. Comprehensively, the *syn-periplaner* (*sp*), *syn-clinal* (*sc*) conformations are referred as *syn* and *anti-clinal* (*ac*) and *anti-periplaner* (*ap*) conformations are broadly referred as *anti*. The conformations are assigned based on the dihedral angle (θ) between nitrogen atom of α -amino group, chiral carbon atom, carbonyl carbon atom of carboxylic group and oxygen atom of carboxylic group of substrate AA (shown in Fig. 2). Therefore, the pair of oxygen atoms can be distinguished based on their respective conformations. The separation between the pair of

Fig. 2. Schematic representations of the *syn* and *anti* conformations of the oxygen atoms of the carboxylic acid group of substrate amino acid relative to the amino group. The dihedral angle of one oxygen of carboxylic acid group is θ_1 and that of the other is θ_2 .

oxygen atoms of the carboxylic acid group of substrate AA and α P atom of ATP in reactant state and the conformation of the two oxygen atoms are shown in the Table 1.

The attacking oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group of substrate AA forms a bond with the α P atom of ATP in the product state. While no such bond formed between the α P atom of ATP and the remaining oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group of substrate AA in the product

Table 1. The separation between the pair of oxygen atoms of carboxylic acid group of substrate AA and α P atom of ATP, designated as ΔR (Å) as calculated from the crystal structure of reactant state of class I and class II aaRSs. The corresponding dihedral angle between the nitrogen atom of α -amino group, the chiral carbon atom, the carbonyl carbon atom and the oxygen atom of carboxylic group (designated as θ_R) are listed. Corresponding conformation based on the crystal structure of various class I and class II aaRSs are also mentioned

aaRS	Class I			Class II		
	θ_R (°)	Conformation	ΔR (Å)	θ_R (°)	Conformation	ΔR (Å)
GluRS	-25.40	<i>syn</i>	2.93	154.61	<i>anti</i>	3.49
GlnRS	67.42	<i>syn</i>	2.96	-112.66	<i>anti</i>	3.30
TyrRS	-61.97	<i>syn</i>	3.52	118.03	<i>anti</i>	3.86
TrpRS	-180.00	<i>anti</i>	3.20	0.00	<i>syn</i>	4.12

aaRS	Class II		
	θ_R (°)	Conformation	ΔR (Å)
HisRS	153.89	<i>anti</i>	2.29
LysRS	171.70	<i>anti</i>	3.10
ProRS	-99.20	<i>anti</i>	3.08

(adenylate) state. The geometry of the corresponding adenylate state of various class I and class II aaRSs are shown in the Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The present analysis shows a significant difference in the mode of nucleophilic

attack by the carboxylic acid group of substrate AA for class I and class II aaRSs. In order to understand the origin of the difference in mode of nucleophilic electrostatic potential (ESP) at the molecular surface of

Fig. 3. Crystal structures of aminoacyl adenylate of various class I aaRSs such as (a) GlnRS, (b) GluRS, (c) LeuRS, (d) ValRS, (e) IleRS, (f) TyrRS, (g) CysRS, (h) MetRS.

Fig. 4. Crystal structures of aminoacyl adenylate of various class II aaRSs such as (a) HisRS, (b) AspRS, (c) AsnRS, (d) AlaRS, (e) GlyRS, (f) ProRS, (g) PheRS and (h) ThrRS.

ATP and AA are analyzed (in absence of all active site residues). The electrostatic potential, $V(\vec{r})$ that the electrons and nuclei of a molecule create at each point \vec{r} in the surrounding space is given by eq. (1).

$$V(\vec{r}) = \sum_A \frac{Z_A}{|\vec{R}_A - \vec{r}|} - \int \frac{\rho(\vec{r}') d\vec{r}'}{|\vec{r}' - \vec{r}|} \quad (1)$$

Z_A is the charge of the nucleus A , located at \vec{R}_A . The electronic density function of the molecule is denoted by $\rho(\vec{r})$ ³¹. The first term of the eq. (1) indicates the contribution of the nuclei and the second term indicates the contribution of the electron. When the magnitude of the first term is greater than the second term, then $V(\vec{r})$ is positive which indicates an electron deficient center. Alternatively, it can be said work done (equivalent to energy) to bring a unit positive charge from infinity to that point is positive or unfavorable. When the magnitude of the second term is greater than the first term, then $V(\vec{r})$ is negative which indicates an electron rich center. Alterna-

tively, it can be said work done (equivalent to energy) done to bring a unit positive charge from infinity to that point is negative or favorable. The ESP analysis is carried out for GluRS (representative of class I) and LysRS (representative of class II aaRSs) using HF/6-31G** level of theory as shown in Fig. 5. Gaussian suit of programs is used for the calculation³². The result is discussed in the following section.

Results and discussion

The separations between the pair of oxygen atom of carboxylic acid group of substrate AA and α P atom of ATP and the conformations of the corresponding oxygen atoms for various class I and class II aaRSs in reactant state are shown in the Table 1. As mentioned before, the oxygen atom closer to the attacking center (α P atom of ATP) is the candidate for the attack. The analysis shows that out of the four available crystal structure of class I aaRSs the conformation of the closest oxygen is *syn* for

Fig. 5. Electrostatic potential on the molecular surfaces of ATP and (a) GluRS, (b) LysRS in the reactant state as present in the crystal structure of the corresponding aaRSs. The ESP calculations are performed using HF/6-31G** level of theory with isodensity value of 0.0004 au. The color variation ranges from red (electronegative) to blue (electropositive) with the ESP values ranging from -0.5 to $+0.5$ au. The ATP region is significantly electronegative as discussed in text.

three and *anti* for one. In contrast, out of three available crystal structure of class II aaRSs the conformation of the closest oxygen is *anti* for all three. The result indicates a significant difference in the mode of in-line attack of the oxygen atom of the carboxylic group of substrate AA to the α P atom of ATP for class I and class II aaRSs. The *syn* oxygen atom of the carboxylic group attacks the α P of ATP in class I aaRSs, while the *anti* oxygen atom attacks in the case of class II aaRSs. This is reported for the first time to the best of our knowledge.

The study is confirmed by further analysis of the conformation of the oxygen atom in the adenylate state as shown in Table 2. Out of eight available crystal structures of adenylate state of class I aaRSs, the conformation of the oxygen atom covalently linked with α P (attacking

Table 2. The dihedral angle between the nitrogen atom of α -amino group, the chiral carbon atom, the carbonyl carbon atom and the oxygen atom of carboxylic group covalently linked with α P in the adenylate state (designated as θ_p) as well as conformation of the corresponding oxygen atom for various class I and class II aaRSs based on the available crystal structure

aaRS	Class I		Class II		
	θ_p ($^\circ$)	Conformation	aaRS	θ_p ($^\circ$)	Conformation
GlnRS	-0.76	<i>syn</i>	HisRS	164.07	<i>anti</i>
GluRS	39.09	<i>syn</i>	AspRS	169.52	<i>anti</i>
LeuRS	-1.75	<i>syn</i>	AsnRS	145.75	<i>anti</i>
ValRS	14.98	<i>syn</i>	AlaRS	171.62	<i>anti</i>
IleRS	4.34	<i>syn</i>	GlyRS	-169.39	<i>anti</i>
TyrRS	-51.01	<i>syn</i>	PheRS	-123.42	<i>anti</i>
CysRS	-27.09	<i>syn</i>	ThrRS	161.02	<i>anti</i>
MetRS	-12.60	<i>syn</i>	ProRS	-166.37	<i>anti</i>

oxygen) is *sp* for six and *sc* for two aaRS. This is shown in Fig. 3. Again, in contrast, out of the nine crystal structures of adenylate state of class II aaRSs, the conformation of the oxygen covalently linked with α P (attacking oxygen) is *ap* for six and *ac* for three. This is shown in Fig. 4. Consequently, the attacking oxygen atom of substrate amino acid has (both in reactant and product state) *syn* (either *sc* or *sp*) conformation with respect to the α -amino group for class I aaRS. In contrast, the attacking oxygen atoms of the substrate amino acid have *anti* (either *ap* or *ac*) conformation with respect to the α -amino group in all class II aaRS investigated. To the best of our knowledge, this difference in the reaction mechanism of first step of aminoacylation reaction is noted for the first time.

The origin of the attack of *syn* oxygen in class I aaRSs and *anti* oxygen attack in class II aaRSs can be explained from the ESP analysis of the substrates (AA and ATP) in absence of the active site residues. The analyses are carried out for various class I and class II aaRSs as shown in Fig. 5(a-g). An imaginary plane is considered which is almost parallel to the sugar ring of ATP and nearly perpendicular to the adenosine base as well as passing through the O_5' atom of sugar ring. The carboxylic acid group of the substrate AA lies perpendicular to the imaginary plane and the amino group remains above the plane for both aaRS. While the substrate AA is oriented in the same direction relative to the plane in aaRSs, the orientation of

the ATP is opposite in the two cases. The triphosphate group of ATP in class I aaRSs such as GluRS is above the plane while the same is below in the case of class II aaRSs such as LysRS. In other words, the relative arrangement of the ATP with respect to the AA is different in class I and class II aaRSs. Since both the triphosphate group of ATP and carboxylic acid group of AA contains negative charges, it is favorable for the *syn* oxygen atom to be proximal with α P and the *anti* oxygen atom can be directed away from the charge distribution of ATP in class I aaRSs to minimize the repulsive interaction. This is shown in Fig. 5(a). In contrast, the orientation of ATP being exactly opposite in class II aaRSs, it is favorable for *anti* oxygen atom to be proximal with α P and the *syn* oxygen atom remain away from the charge distribution of ATP (Fig. 5(b)). The *syn* oxygen atom is closer to the α P of ATP in case of class I aaRSs and acts as the attacking atom. In contrast, the *anti* oxygen is closer to the α P of ATP in case of class II aaRSs and acts as the attacking atom. The spatial arrangements of ATP and AA in all other class I and class II aaRS as concluded from the respective adenylate geometries (shown in Figs. 3 and 4) confirm that the foregoing reasoning is generally valid for the other class I and class II aaRSs as well.

The difference in the mode of attack (either by *syn* oxygen or by *anti* oxygen) leads to different arrangement of atoms at the reaction center (location of the nucleophilic attack between the carboxylic acid group of amino acid and the α -phosphorous atom of ATP, denoted as α P). The active site residues or ions of aaRSs have complementary interaction (electrostatic or hydrophobic) with the nearby substrate and is expected to be dependent on the spatial arrangement of atoms nearby). The chemical structures of the respective substrate like amino acid differ only in the side chain parts near the reaction center from one aaRS to the other. It will be worthwhile to investigate the correlation between the microscopic difference in the reaction mechanism in the two aaRS and the variation in the active site structures in the two classes. Studies are ongoing in this direction. This is expected to provide significant knowledge about the active site structure and catalytic activity which has important implication in designing novel artificial enzyme mimetic systems.

Concluding remarks

The present work reveals a significant microscopic difference in the common scheme of nucleophilic reaction of the activation step of aminoacylation reaction. The relative arrangement of the negative charge distribution of the oxygen atoms of the ATP and that of the carboxylic acid group of AA are directed in opposite directions in class I (GluRS, GlnRS, TyrRS, TrpRS, LeuRS, ValRS, IleRS, CysRS, MetRS) and class II aaRSs (HisRS, LysRS, ProRS, AspRS, AsnRS, AlaRS, GlyRS, PheRS, ThrRS). The dissimilar relative orientations of the AA and ATP in the two class of aaRSs and the concomitant variations in ESP result in two modes of attack in the two cases. It is favorable for the *syn* oxygen atom to be proximal with α P and acts as the attacking atom and the *anti* oxygen atom can be directed away from the charge distribution of ATP in class I aaRSs to minimize the repulsive interaction. In contrast, the orientation of ATP being exactly opposite in class II aaRSs, it is favorable for *anti* oxygen atom to be proximal with α P acts as the attacking atom and the *syn* oxygen atom remain away from the charge distribution of ATP. As a result, it is favorable for the *syn* oxygen atom to act as the attacking atom in the nucleophilic reaction in class I aaRSs. In contrast, it is favorable for the *anti* oxygen atom in class II aaRSs to act as the attacking atom in the activation step.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by a grant from DST, India. SDB thanks University of Kalyani for a research scholarship. SD thanks CSIR for a JRF.

References

1. D. L. Nelson and M. M. Cox, "Lehninger Principles of Biochemistry", 4th ed., W. H. Freeman & Co., New York, 2002.
2. J. M. Berg, J. L. Tymoczko and S. Stryer, "Biochemistry", W. H. Freeman & Co., New York, 2002.
3. J. G. Arnez and D. Moras, *Trends Biochem. Sci.*, 1997, **22**, 211.
4. M. Ibba and D. Söll, *Annu. Rev. Biochem.*, 2000, **69**, 617.
5. G. Eriani, M. Delarue, O. Poch, J. Gangloff and D. Moras, *Nature*, 1990, **347**, 203.
6. M. Delarue and D. Moras, *BioEssays*, 1993, **15**, 675.
7. I. A. Vasil'eva and N. A. Moor, *Biochemistry*, 2007, **72**, 247.

8. S. Dutta Banik and N. Nandi, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 2301.
9. S. Dutta Banik and N. Nandi, *Biophys. Chem.*, 2011, **158**, 61.
10. E. L. Eliel and S. H. Wilen, "Stereochemistry of Organic Compound", Wiley-Interscience Publication, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1993.
11. S. Sekine, O. Nureki, D. Y. Dubois, S. Bernier, R. Chenevert, J. Lapointe, D. G. Vassylyev and S. Yokoyama, *EMBO J.*, 2003, **22**, 676.
12. J. J. Perona, M. A. Rould and T. A. Steitz, *Biochemistry*, 1993, **32**, 8758.
13. V. L. Rath, L. F. Silvan, B. Beijer, B. S. Sproat and T. A. Steitz, *Structure*, 1998, **6**, 439.
14. I. Gruic-Sovulj, N. Uter, T. Bullock and J. J. Perona, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2005, **280**, 23978.
15. A. Yaremchuk, I. Kriklivyi, M. Tukalo and S. Cusack, *EMBO J.*, 2002, **21**, 3829.
16. P. Brick, T. N. Bhat and D. M. Blow *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1989, **208**, 83.
17. P. Retaillieu, X. Huang, Y. Yin, M. Hu, V. Weinreb, P. Vachette, C. Vonrhein, G. Bricogne, P. Roversi, V. Ilyin. (Jr.) and C. W. Carter, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 2003, **325**, 39.
18. J. G. Arnez, J. G. Augustine, D. Moras and C. S. Francklyn, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (USA)*, 1997, **94**, 7144.
19. A. Yaremchuk, M. Tukalo, M. Grötli and S. Cusack, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 2001, **309**, 989.
20. G. Desogus, F. Todone, P. Brick and S. Onesti, *Biochemistry*, 2000, **39**, 8418.
21. S. Sekine, O. Nureki, D. Y. Dubois, S. Bernier, R. Chenevert, J. Lapointe, D. G. Vassylyev and S. Yokoyama, *EMBO J.*, 2003, **22**, 676.
22. T. L. Lincecum (Jr.), M. Tukalo, A. Yaremchuk, R. S. Mursinna, A. M. Williams, B. S. Sproat, W. V. D. Eynde, A. Link, S. V. Calenbergh, M. Grötli, S. A. Martinis and S. Cusack, *Mol. Cell*, 2003, **11**, 951.
23. S. Fukai, O. Nureki, S. Sekine, A. Shimada, J. Tao, D. G. Vassylyev and S. Yokoyama, *Cell*, 2000, **103**, 793.
24. T. Nakama, O. Nureki and S. Yokoyama, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2001, **276**, 47387.
25. S. Eiler, A. C. Dock-Bregeon, L. Moulinier, J. C. Thierry and D. Moras, *EMBO J.*, 1999, **18**, 6532.
26. T. Crepin, F. Peterson, M. Haertlein, D. Jensen, C. Wang, S. Cusack and M. Kron, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 2011, **405**, 1056.
27. M. Guo, Y. E. Chong, R. Shapiro, K. Beebe, X. L. Yang and P. Schimmel, *Nature*, 2009, **462**, 808.
28. J. G. Arnez, A. C. Dock-Bregeon and D. Moras, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1999, **286**, 1449.
29. L. Reshetnikova, N. Moor, O. Lavrik and D. G. Vassylyev, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1999, **287**, 555.
30. A. Torres-Larios, A. C. Dock-Bregeon, P. Romby, B. Rees, R. Sankaranarayanan, J. Caillet and M. Springer, *Nat. Struct. Biol.*, 2002, **9**, 343.
31. P. Sjöberg and P. Politzer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1990, **94**, 3959.
32. M. J. Frisch *et al.*, Gaussian 03, revision C.02; Gaussian, Inc.: Wallingford, CT, 2004.